

S P A T I A L

GUIDING LIGHT IN THE AI LANDSCAPE

Illuminating the Path to a Trustworthy AI Ecosystem

1st July 2024

TU Delft Faculty of Technology, Policy and Management
Jaffalaan 5, 2628BX, Delft

DISCUSSIONS,
NETWORKING OPPORTUNITIES,
POSTER SESSIONS & MORE!

PROJECT PARTNERS

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